

RESPONDENT

D7.1 – RESPONDENT Website

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PROJECT PARTNERS

Partner	Country	Short name
FUTURE INTELLIGENCE EREVNA TILEPIKINONIAKON KE PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON EPE	Greece	FINT
FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	Spain	VICOM
CARR COMMUNICATIONS LIMITED	Ireland	CARR
KIEFER TEK ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS	Greece	KIEFER
GREENESCO ENERGEIAKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA	Greece	GREEN
ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA	Spain	EPESA
FUNDACIO INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'ENERGIA DE CATALUNYA	Spain	IREC-CERCA
ELECTROTECNICA DEL URUMEA SL	Spain	EUSKABEA

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Definition
EU	European Union
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the RESPONDENT Project Website, which has been set up in the fulfilment of Task 7.1 – *Communication and Dissemination Activities, including Stakeholder Engagement* within Work Package 7, as specified in the Description of Action. The deliverable explains the conceptual choices that were made in designing the project website. It also outlines the work that has been done in creating an impactful visual identity of the RESPONDENT project, which guided the website design.

The report includes a detailed description of the landing page, which welcomes visitors to the project website. It also presents an overview of future developments and planned updates as the project advances to next stages. The deliverable also includes useful information on the sections and navigations on the website, as well as opportunities for visitors to get in touch with the RESPONDENT project.

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1 Introduction

Establishing the digital identity of a brand is a key component of an effective communication and dissemination strategy, beginning with the creation of a dedicated website. The website serves as the main public medium through which external stakeholders and interested parties are introduced to the RESPONDENT project, and acts as a vital resource in projecting the project's brand with a fixed online presence. It is therefore of the utmost importance to design the website having the user in mind.

Improvements in the technologies used to optimise website performance and usability has shifted the paradigm of web design to the user-centred approach. It values the user experience and guides the decision of what the website should look like, with the best modern websites being simple and easy to navigate from the offset. They contain all relevant information in the homepage, or at least within a single click of it. Another trend, which shows a steady growth in the EU, is the active use of the internet while on the move via mobile and portable devices [1]. These trends indicate that websites need to have an impactful visual identity, a coherent structure, streamlined navigation compatible with multiple devices (i.e., a responsive design), and well-presented content that is accessible for a diverse range of audiences.

The RESPONDENT brand name, typeface, layout, logo, and colour palette, which can be viewed in the below graphic, were developed in conjunction with the input and/or approval of project partners and were initially presented at the project kick-off meeting. The colour palette is one of the most important visual elements of the RESPONDENT brand, serving to highlight the content and create a seamless scrolling experience between different sections of the website. In addition, the RESPONDENT Twitter and LinkedIn accounts were established to coincide and support the project website. Together, these various channels will be crucial components of the RESPONDENT brand, indicating that the brand identity of RESPONDENT has been developed and is being put into practice.

Figure 1: The RESPONDENT Brand

The initial layout of the RESPONDENT website, its structure, and the information included were developed in cooperation with project partners. All partners contributed to the initial content for the website at launch. As project activities start to take place over the coming months, partners will be encouraged to contribute further to the development of the RESPONDENT website through blogposts, research notes, and updates on the status of their work within the project. The website will continue to evolve over the project’s lifetime with regular updates, uploads of publications, research materials, and interactive content, such as social media feeds and explanatory videos.

1.1 Document Summary Outline

This deliverable describes the development of the RESPONDENT project website, which includes its core structure, layout, the initial content at the time of the website launch, and the plan for future updates. In this report, each section of the project website will be identified with its purpose, content to date, and future use. The report also underlines the importance of the RESPONDENT project website as the nucleus of an all-encompassing public platform for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities envisioned within the RESPONDENT Project.

1.2 Addressing the RESPONDENT Description of Action

The following table presents the connection of the contents of the present deliverable with the RESPONDENT Grant Agreement requirements in Work Package 7:

RESPONDENT Description of Action requirements	Deliverable addressing the requirements	Brief description
Task 7.1 Communication and Dissemination Activities, including Stakeholder Engagement	D7.1 Respondent Website	The action is part of the RESPONDENT Brand strategy, which aims to develop RESPONDENT as a recognised brand among those working in the field of renewable energy sources (RES). The objective is to set out a firm communication strategy and to produce professional-grade communication material by establishing the appropriate dissemination channels and developing communication means, such as the project website. The RESPONDENT website will serve as the nucleus for project dissemination and communication, as well as a repository for project information, research outputs and deliverables.

Table 1: Description of Action: Task 7.1

1.3 Intended Readership

The RESPONDENT project website includes information and updates of all current project activities, with plans to develop such activities as the work of the project progresses. It serves as an essential communication tool, which helps to increase visibility of research activities of the consortium members and outcomes of the project. As such, this report is important for all members of the project consortium. All external communication and dissemination activities will be displayed on the website as they are carried out by the partners.

The report is also of interest to the European Research Executive Agency and the European Commission, European and international organisations, and national authorities with interest in the further utilisation of RES as an alternative to traditional fossil fuels. The website will include updates and events with cluster Horizon Europe projects in RES, so it will be beneficial for other research projects operating in the same domain as RESPONDENT.

This report is further intended for consumption by members of the public. It will provide insights into the structure and the overview of the RESPONDENT project website as well as the conceptual foundation behind its development.

1.4 Relationship with other RESPONDENT Deliverables and Tasks

The RESPONDENT project website will play a central role in communicating all major project developments, research activities, and outcomes throughout the lifecycle of the project. The website serves as a hub for all project external communications and will feature regular updates on the project. The website will be an essential communication tool in exploiting the project's end-results and marketing the RESPONDENT technology, systems, and innovations as spearheading the EU's ambition towards a carbon-neutral economy by 2050. Furthermore, the website ensures that RESPONDENT is recognised as an EU-wide brand that is leading the EU's shift towards an increased adoption of RES.

The website will also play a significant role in knowledge sharing of innovation and technological developments in the field of RES and their utilisation. All project deliverables, after being approved by the Project Officer, will be uploaded to the website for the purpose of transparency and information-sharing. These uploads will include public deliverable reports in their entirety, and executive summaries of confidential deliverables.

2 RESPONDENT Website Structure

2.1 Landing Page

The RESPONDENT website is available at respondent-project.eu

The landing page, as seen in the graphic below, welcomes visitors to the RESPONDENT website with a bright, uncluttered layout and moving images, as well as the project title and a specially designed background.

Figure 2: Website Landing Page

Crucially, it is possible to reach every page of the current website in just one click from the landing page as the website continues to be developed with simplicity and ease of access in mind.

The landing page has been structured to capture visitors' attention and provide them with all the information they need to continue browsing. The 'About The Project', 'Get In Contact' and 'Project Partners' sections have been identified as being of most immediate relevance to the majority of visitors, with the potential for additional sections to be added as the project progresses. Dynamic elements have also been introduced, positioning these pages at the front of the project website to take priority in the development stage of the website.

2.2 About RESPONDENT

When visitors first arrive to the website and scroll down through the landing page, they will be presented with a brief, high-level description of the RESPONDENT project. This section has been kept intentionally short, as it will serve the simple purpose of answering some of the introductory questions that visitors may have about the project, including what RESPONDENT is, what it aims to achieve, and the solutions that it offers to increase the uptake of RES in the EU.

WHAT IS RESPONDENT?

As the EU seeks to transition from a system of legacy energy and an over-reliance on fossil fuels to a new era of clean, sustainable energy, the bloc has been seeking dynamic and effective ways to turn this vision into a reality.

Although the EU has made significant strides in increasing its use of renewable energy sources (RES), more needs to be done if the most calamitous effects of climate change are to be mitigated or reversed. Furthermore, the desire of the EU to shift away from fossil fuels, the majority of which are imported, would also leave it less exposed to external geopolitical factors that threaten the energy security of the bloc.

With these points in mind, the RESPONDENT project aims to develop and promote the integration of RES into Europe's existing power grids, as well as to demonstrate their viability and reliability compared to traditional sources of energy that are wreaking havoc on global temperatures and accelerating the most destructive impacts of our rapidly changing climate.

Led by FINT, the RESPONDENT consortium consists of experts in the fields of energy transition, information and communication technologies, construction, research, and more, made up of 8 partner organisations from 3 countries across Europe.

Figure 3: What is RESPONDENT?

Figure 4: RESPONDENT Solutions

2.3 RESPONDENT Project Partners

Following a brief description of the RESPONDENT project, a slideshow is featured that displays the logos of all 8 project partners.

As RESPONDENT consists of partners who bring an array of experience, networks, and expertise to the project, the slideshow of logos will enhance the trustworthiness of the project for first-time visitors to the website, as well as for those who have been directed to the website by one of the partners.

PROJECT PARTNERS

Figure 5: Project Partners Slideshow

At the top of the landing page, the viewer will also have the opportunity to learn more about the partners and their respective organisations in-depth by clicking on the ‘Project Partners’ title. As seen in the example of CARR Communications below, visitors to the website will be presented with an overview of the partner organisation, their specific role in the RESPONDENT project, and a link to their company website.

CARR COMMUNICATIONS

Location: [Dublin, Ireland](#)

Website: [Carr Communications](#)

PARTNER OVERVIEW

Founded in 1973, Carr Communications is Ireland's leading provider of public relations, dissemination, exploitation and training consultancy to individuals and businesses across Ireland.

Carr Communications provides strategic communications consultancy and training to clients in both the public and private sector.

Our team has experience in every aspect of communications, including strategic communications planning, event management, media relations, media training, reputation management, issue and crisis management, government relations, stakeholder engagement, internal communications, social media and video production.

PARTNER PROJECT ROLE

Carr Communications serves as the Communication and Dissemination Manager in the RESPONDENT project as part of WP7 – Roadmap to Impact.

Carr Communications is responsible for the overall development of the RESPONDENT brand, for coordinating impactful communications on behalf of the project, and for engaging key stakeholders with RESPONDENT's ongoing activities and project end results.

Figure 6: Project Partners Page

2.4 Contact

The RESPONDENT website also features a contact section, which will facilitate easier communication for external stakeholders and interested parties who wish to learn more about the project. This section currently features the contact information of WP1 and WP7 managers.

3 Future Developments of the Website

As with any project of this scope and scale, the RESPONDENT Website will be continuously refined and updated throughout the lifecycle of the project as progress is made, tasks are completed, and deliverables are published. The input of all partners will therefore be sought on an ongoing basis to ensure that the website is fully optimised and in line with the vision of the project.

Per the information contained within RESPONDENT's Grant Agreement, the overarching objective of the website is to serve as the nucleus of online dissemination throughout the lifetime of project and until 2030. In addition, it is also intended that the RESPONDENT website will act as a vital resource in raising awareness/promoting the project to key stakeholders through project branding and a fixed online presence.

4 Conclusions

The initial structure and content of the RESPONDENT project website has been created with a view to future brand development, encompassing the wider dissemination and communication strategy of RESPONDENT.

As the project is still in its infancy, the website in its current iteration is intentionally minimal. However, the overall appearance and content of the website will gradually develop and broaden as the activities of RESPONDENT progress over its 30-month lifecycle. Updates to the website will therefore be attractive and engaging to visitors who wish to keep abreast of RESPONDENT's ongoing work and accomplishments.

Bearing in mind the fundamental goal of creating the RESPONDENT website, which is to serve as the nucleus of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the project, the website has been created so that it is visually appealing, easily navigable, and informative to all identified stakeholders. As such, the RESPONDENT website has already begun to demonstrate itself as an accurate representation of the RESPONDENT brand, as well as being a future repository of all information and outputs pertaining to the work of the project.

References

- [1] Feeling Peaky (2018) 9 Principles of Good Web Design. Retrieved 12 December 2022
<https://www.feelingpeaky.com/9-principles-of-good-web-design/>